

**THE ROLE OF SCIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MORAL-AESTHETIC CULTURE
IN FUTURE TEACHERS**

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The huge reforms of our republic on the way of building an independent legal, democratic state, free civil culture brought new conditions to the publication of the human essence, raising the spiritual and intellectual potential of specialists with future higher education, full realization of their opportunities, perfection of moral and aesthetic culture.

These conditions, in turn, gave birth to the scientific-theoretical and practical-methodical heritage created by human intelligence, new demand for man himself, new attitude. The President Of The Republic M. Mirziyayev said in his speeches: "it is clear to all of us that every person in our country, every family's most cherished dreams, life interests, above all, will be manifested and realized in the image of his children. Of course, we will mobilize all our forces and opportunities in this regard..." as they say, teachers should become the basis of their professional activities. In this case, first of all, the task of self-perfection of man in all aspects, the formation and development of him as a perfect person, ensuring the creation of omillarni, is necessary and relevant as ever [1].

In the content of an excellent, comprehensively developed personality, the moral-aesthetic culture of the future specialist plays an important role. A specialist society, whose moral-aesthetic culture is truly formed, is a person who pursues the interests of the people, comprehensively understands their duty and responsibility, approaches the motherland, society, the people, values, activities, nature, the future from the point of view of human qualities.

It is known that the moral-aesthetic culture of future specialists-young people is inextricably formed in the process of the entire educational system of higher educational institutions. In this process, socio-economic and humanitarian Sciences occupy a leading position. "History of Uzbekistan", "jurisprudence", "Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "philosophy", "fundamentals of spirituality", "theory of Economics", "Sociology", "pedagogy and psychology", "the idea of national identity: basic concepts and principles" and other disciplines that take place in the

curriculum of Higher Education introduce students to the scientific-philosophical and ideological aspects of society, political, cultural and spiritual life, the history of the country, economy, material existence and social life:

- young people's new attitude to Nature, Society, activity;
- conscious discipline and intelligent labor culture;
- moral-aesthetic knowledge, feelings;
- helps to educate intolerance against negative ills and alien ideas [2].

In fact, the history of Uzbekistan on the topics of which" the history of Uzbekistan " ranks as the content of science is an integral part of the history of mankind, it is one of the ancient foci of human civilization, the contribution of our ancestors to the world civilization is enormous in the development of spirituality, culture, enlightenment of the peoples of the world, , issues on the fact that legal democracy is an important impetus for the restoration of the foundations of the state and civil society are a thorough source of development and perfection of young people, active lifestyle and ready to carry out mass-political activities, moral and aesthetic culture is the education of a high specialist.

It is worth noting that it is difficult to imagine the rise of humanity, the development of society and the country without culture and spirituality. The program of the course" culturology "includes the following subjects:" ancient culture of the peoples of Central Asia"," culture of the Eastern Awakening"," culture of the era of Temur and Temurids"," culture of the Uzbek people in the era of the despotic Soviet state"," national independence and cultural development in Uzbekistan"," fundamentals of spirituality"," spirituality, economy and their interconnectedness"," the role of spirituality in politics, law and power"," To give information on the formation of the moral, aesthetic, legal culture of the ancient Uzbek peoples in the study of such subjects as" faith, faithfulness, justice, compassion, purity and loyalty-moral qualities of the individual"," legal literacy, obedience to the law, respect for the state system and loyalty to the civil duty criteria of personality perfection "and to convey their importance for the current socio-political, you know what? It should also be remembered that the ideas in the content of the mentioned topics are an important source for educating an independent thinker, a specialist who has a deep understanding of self -, self -, language, culture, spiritual heritage and translating these qualities into the criterion of his moral and aesthetic culture, every teacher of social and humanitarian science of Higher Education.

In this direction, subjects such as "pedagogy", "Professional Psychology", which are in the first block of the educational plan of higher education, are also of educational and educational importance. Topics such as "goals and objectives of Education of the harmonious generation", "moral and moral education of the younger generation", "ideological-political (ideological), physical, professional and labor of the harmonious generation", economic, legal, environmental, nafosat, civil education are also important criteria of moral-aesthetic culture-humanity, justice, humanism, patriotism, kindness, patience, commitment to duty, Labor love for the family serves as an important factor in the absorption of such feelings in students.

After studying each subject of the courses, as an independent work "there is no future without historical memory", "human beauty in spirituality", "what could I do to strengthen independence? Writing and analyzing abstracts on topics such as" culturalism is the main criterion of humanity", "faith, faith-e'tiqod in my imagination", "if you glorify a Person, Allah will glorify you " will help students to form a moral-aesthetic culture.

The result of our research conducted in the fields of experience in this direction shows that the formation of the moral-aesthetic culture of students is not only in the lessons, but also in extracurricular activities, events, continuation, "what can I do for the happiness of my motherland and people?", "The personality of civil society in my imagination", " how can I show my loyalty to the people, to the motherland, to my parents?"let such problems become the daily problem, duty, responsibility of the students, let them be interested, direct. Then we will educate civil society a specialist with a moral and aesthetic qualities.

The above-mentioned views made the issue of Organization of educational work on the basis of deep knowledge of the students in the process of education of the higher educational institution, especially in the socio-Humanitarian category, an extremely topical issue. In such conditions, teachers of socio-humanitarian categories operating in the educational institution should not only be perfectly aware of the disciplines being taught, be skilful educators, but also be an example of a high moral-aesthetic outlook for students, that is, they should be the embodiment of moral purity, moral beauty, aesthetic taste, aesthetic ideal, aesthetic consciousness. At the same time, as the experience shows, every future teacher of vocational education should know and act on the basis of psychological and physiologic features in all respects[3-4].

LITERATURE:

1. Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an invincible force. T.: Spirituality, 2008, - 176 p.
2. Sh.M.Mirziyayev: speech dedicated to the 24 anniversary of our Constitution.
3. Philosophy: encyclopedic dictionary: (developer and responsible editor q.Nazarov). - T.: East, 2004.- 496 p
4. Sharifkho'jayev M. Formation of an open civil society in Uzbekistan. - T.: East, 2003. – 512p.